

Effect of Solvent Polarity on the $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ Transition of 3-phenylsydnone.

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Of the known mesoionic compounds¹ sydnone derivatives² (I & II) are fairly well-investigated. Among other properties³, the five membered heterocyclic system is characterised^{1,2}, by a long-wavelength band at 290-340 m μ (ϵ , $\sim$ 5000-8000) which has been well-correlated by MO to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition⁴.

Closely related mesoionic 1,3,4-thiadiazoles (III) similarly exhibit¹ a long wavelength $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition ($\lambda_{\text{max}} \times 360\text{-}420$ m μ). In connection with our recent work⁵ on substituted III, it was observed⁶ that the characteristic $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ band displayed solvent sensitivity (blue shift) which is usually attributed to $\pi=\pi^*$ transitions. Due to isoelectronic nature of the two systems (I and III), information on the solvent sensitivity of $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition in I is anticipated to be rewarding to the extent that some controversy^{1,7} is still raging regarding the relative importance of contributing mesomeric forms to the total structure of I.

Thus, using 3-phenylsydnone as a prototype, the λ_{max} corresponding to $\pi\text{-}\pi^*$ transition shows a regular blue shift with increased polarity (Z -values⁸) of the solvent. In fact, good linearity could be discerned graphically between transition energy (ΔE_{T}) and Z values. This is similar to our previous⁶ experience on III. However, data corresponding to carbon tetrachloride show serious deviation. This could be reasonably attributed to self-association, possibly dimerization, in a non-polar solvent, as in the case of fatty acids.

Again, qualitatively similar conclusions are derived by inspection of data from a series of chloroform-cyclohexane mixtures containing increased proportion of cyclohexane. Thus, although solute concentration remains the same, linearity tends to break down with

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about 80% cyclohexane and becomes more prominent with 90% cyclohexane in the mixture. Presumably, high dipole moment (6.48 D)¹ of 3-phenylsydnone is an important factor to be reckoned with for this tendency to self association.

In summary, it is reasonable to assume that inspite of 2p- π interaction, the exocyclic C-O bond in I is more "carbonyl" in character than implied by structure II. This is in agreement with known^{1,2} bond length (1.20 Å) and carbonyl stretching frequencies (1720 $\pm$ 20 Cm^{-1}) in I. Under the circumstances, the observed behaviour (blue shift) in polar solvents could be reconciled by assuming participation of the lone pair electrons (exo-oxygen) with solvent molecules. The situation is, therefore, analogous to that prevailing in N-methyl substituted hydrazones⁹. From the calculated values of ΔE_T , it is further apparent that in the given instances the solvent-solute interaction is quite appreciable.

The required 3-phenylsydnone, m.p. 135°, lit.¹⁰ m.p. 134-134.5°, λ_{max} 410 $\text{m}\mu$, was synthesised by known method and the solvents were either AR grade (E. Merck) or purified according to Vogel¹¹. Spectral data were obtained with Hilger automatic recording spectrophotometer in 1 c.m. matched quartz cells at $26 \pm 1^\circ$. The accuracy of wavelength measurement is $\pm 0.5 \text{ m}\mu$.

Transition energies were calculated from the relation, $\Delta E_T = 286 \times 10^3 / \lambda$ (Å°).

TABLE I

Spectral data on the effect of solvent polarity on the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^$ transition of 3-phenylsydnone*

Solvent	Z-values Kcal/mole	λ_{max} $\text{m}\mu$	ϵ_{max}	ΔE_T kcal/mole
1. Methanol	83.6	310	5010	92.26
2. Ethanol	79.6	311	6130	91.96
3. Isopropanol	76.3	312.5	4930	91.52
4. Acetonitrile	71.3	313	4730	91.37
5. Chloroform	63.2	315	4830	90.79
6. Carbo, tetrachloride	<63**	323	4910	88.54
7. Chloroform with varying amounts of cyclohexane *(CYH)				
(a) 20% CYH		315	4770	
(b) 40% CYH		315	4750	
(c) 60% CYH		316	4670	
(d) 80% CYH		317	4230	
(e) 90% CYH		320	4480	

*Solute Conc'n = 2.503×10^{-4} moles/L

**Z = 60.1 for cyclohexane, so expected value for CCl_4 is between 60 and 63 Kcal/mole.

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